

Acoustic Guitar

Flageolet

Drumset

Drumset

Drumset

Hi-hat

Thundersheet

5

Guit.

Fla.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

9

Guit.

12

Guit.

15

Guit.

Fla.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

18

Guit.

Fla.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

21

Guit.
 Fla.
 Drs.
 Drs.
 Drs.
 Hi-hat
 Thu.

24

Guit.
 Fla.
 Drs.
 Drs.
 Drs.
 Hi-hat
 Thu.

Musical score for guitar, flute, drums, hi-hat, and tuba. The score is divided into six staves. The guitar staff (Guit.) features a treble clef and a capo on the 8th fret, with chords in the first three measures. The flute staff (Fla.) has a treble clef and a capo on the 8th fret, with a melodic line in the first three measures. The drums (Drs.) are represented by three staves with a drum set icon, showing various drum patterns. The hi-hat (Hi-hat) staff uses a drum set icon and 'x' marks to indicate hi-hat patterns. The tuba (Thu.) staff uses a drum set icon and notes to indicate tuba patterns. The score is divided into three measures.